

**THE ROLE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN
ENSURING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN GENERAL SECONDARY,
SECONDARY SPECIAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS AND IMPLEMENTING PROSECUTOR'S CONTROL OVER
LEGAL COMPLIANCE**

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Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада умумий ўрта, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим муассасаларида қонунчилик ижроси устидан прокурор назоратини амалга оширишда замонавий ахборот технологияларининг роли тўғрисида қимматли маълумотлар қиёсий-ҳуқуқий таҳлил усулидан фойдаланган ҳолда ўрганиб чиқилиб, тизим салоҳиятини оширишга қаратилган таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: прокурор назорати, прокуратура органлари, вояга етмаганлар, замонавий ахборот технологиялари, таълим муассасалари, мақсадли қарорлар қабул қилиш, хавфларни идентификациялаш, ресурсларни тақсимлаш, профилактика чоралар, норматив ҳужжатларга мувофиқлик, кенгайтирилган алоқа, ахборотга асосланган қарорларни қабул қилиш, кузатув ва хавфсизлик тизимлари, биометрик давомат тизимлари.

Аннотация. В данной статье методом сравнительно-правового анализа исследована ценная информация о роли современных информационных технологий в осуществлении прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства в учреждениях общего среднего, среднего специального и профессионального образования, а также разработаны предложения, направленные на повышение потенциала данной системы.

Ключевые слова: прокурорский надзор, органы прокуратуры, несовершеннолетние, современные информационные технологии, образовательные учреждения, целевое принятие решений, выявление рисков, распределение ресурсов, превентивные меры, соблюдение нормативных требований, расширенные коммуникации, принятие решений на основе информации, системы наблюдения и безопасности, биометрические системы учета посещаемости.

Abstract. In this article, valuable information about the role of modern information technologies in the implementation of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions is studied using the method of comparative legal analysis, and proposals aimed at increasing the potential of the system are developed.

Keywords: prosecutor's supervision, prosecution authorities, juveniles, modern information technologies, educational institutions, targeted decision-making, risk identification, resource allocation, preventive measures, regulatory compliance, enhanced communication, information-based decision-making, surveillance and security systems, biometric attendance systems.

Modern information technologies are bringing about revolutionary changes in various fields, including the protection of education and rights. With the widespread implementation of digital systems and data analysis, prosecutors have acquired powerful tools to establish and implement effective monitoring mechanisms in educational institutions. This article highlights the crucial role of modern information technologies in enabling prosecutors to oversee and ensure the application of legal and regulatory documents in educational institutions, as well as to enhance fairness, accountability, and transparency in the achievement of educational outcomes.

One of the significant advantages of modern information technologies is their capability to efficiently gather large volumes of data. Furthermore, these technologies generate comprehensive and actionable information on the functioning, sustainability, activities, and institutional operations of general, specialized, and vocational

educational institutions. Prosecutors can utilize this information to identify potentially problematic areas, such as the quality of instruction, compliance issues, or financial mismanagement, for further investigation.

Utilizing methods for analyzing complex data allows prosecutors to identify trends in systemic issues within educational systems, which can provide opportunities for implementing preventive measures before problems escalate. Moreover, general, specialized, and vocational educational institutions are governed by a set of regulations and standards established by government authorities. Modern information technologies suggest effective monitoring tools to ensure compliance with these standards. For instance, prosecutors can utilize auditing procedures to evaluate adherence to prescribed curricula, security protocols, and accreditation requirements.

Digital monitoring also aids in identifying and preventing fraudulent practices, such as unauthorized fund allocation by educational management or unauthorized sharing of funds by administrative authorities. Ensuring strict adherence to regulatory documents helps prosecutors safeguard the integrity of the educational system and protect the rights of stakeholders. Additionally, prosecutors can access these systems to obtain information about institutional practices, financial operations, and the decision-making processes for financial transactions and misconduct.

It is essential to emphasize that these comprehensive measures enable prosecutors to monitor and scrutinize the activities conducted by educational administrators, ensuring accountability for any misconduct or illegal activities.

In addition, technology facilitates the dissemination of information to communities, providing parents, students, and the broader community with insights into the activities and operations of educational institutions. However, the use of digital platforms in general, specialized, and vocational educational institutions has also introduced cybersecurity threats. These threats can lead to the compromise of information, potential breaches of payment systems, exposure of confidential data, and disruption of educational processes.

Prosecutorial bodies can play a significant role in mitigating these issues. Collaborating with other law enforcement agencies and cybersecurity experts, they can develop strategies to safeguard confidential information and effectively respond to cyber incidents. As a result, the security and integrity of educational services can be ensured.

In this context, the following ideas expressed by the leader of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, are relevant: "In the current era, characterized by rapid development, who will succeed? It is the state that embraces new ideas, new knowledge, and innovation. Innovation is the future. If we start building our great future today, it must begin precisely with innovative ideas and innovative initiatives" [1].

Emphasizing further, in accordance with the Presidential Decree No. PQ-2833 of March 14, 2017, "On Further Improvement of the System for Preventing Offenses and Combating Crime," one of the main directions of the activities of state bodies and organizations in the field of crime prevention is to enhance cooperation between agencies. It is determined to widely implement modern information and communication technologies, including video surveillance, electronic record-keeping, and mutual exchange of information between institutions, in preventive work.

According to E. Khatov, "If we consider the process of information gathering and utilization (collection, recording, analysis, modification) as part of improving the activities of the prosecutor's office, it can be divided into two main blocks - strengthening information and analytical support"[2].

According to D.V. Gurulev, "The acceptance of decisions on the use of information technologies in the implementation of the main directions of the activities of the prosecutor's office by the prosecutor's office authorities has somewhat reduced the problems of ensuring information security, but they have not been fully resolved.

Analyzing organizational and managerial documents on the use of information technologies by the prosecutor's office authorities in the implementation of the main directions of the activities of the prosecutor's office shows the same inconsistency in

the use of accounting documents, information collection, processing, and storage systems"[3].

According to S. Adilkhodzhaeva and S. Sadikov, "Any state changes in any information space, and, moreover, the task of using the information space to increase the efficiency of governance and management for future generations are also being improved.

Another important task is to bring society and the state closer through information communication"[4]. According to M. Boboev, "Information systems and resources serve to streamline traditional processes, increase speed and efficiency, and make human life exceptional in government agencies and organizations" [5].

In light of these ideas, it is necessary to note that the rapid development of social life in society, the emergence of new social relations, and the establishment of modern mechanisms in the activities of state bodies and institutions, including prosecutorial bodies, are crucial.

Furthermore, in our country, the adoption of Presidential Decree No. PQ-4818, "On Measures to Digitize the Activities of the Judiciary," on September 3, 2020, signifies a significant step towards the widespread implementation of modern technologies in the functioning of the judiciary[6]. The digitization of the activities of the judiciary does not only contribute to transparency and ensuring fairness but also provides the opportunity to expedite the completion of tasks by the employees.

In this regard, the use of digital technologies is essential not only for enhancing the oversight of prosecutors in the sphere of monitoring the activities of government agencies but also for implementing significant improvements in all aspects of prosecutorial work.

In this context, the opinions expressed by legal experts V. Abdeeva and A. Gordeyev emphasize the requirement to use information and communication technologies in the protection of law, particularly within the system of the prosecutor's office. All of these aspects are considered as essential directions for enhancing the efficiency of operations. [7]

According to the emphasized views of Y.P. Yakubina and V.I. Zhaklar, "Digitizing prosecutor's offices provides the staff with the opportunity to expedite their work and swiftly execute assigned tasks". [8] V.N. Isaenkon further adds, "Digitizing the activities of prosecutor's offices, including the supervision of prosecutors, is an essential and beneficial approach to its comprehensive improvement".[9]

We also endorse the ideas of these authors. According to us, digital technologies offer several advantages for prosecutor's offices, including:

- Streamlining investigation processes, reducing the handling of tasks and paperwork, thereby facilitating quicker and more accurate decision-making and acceptance of resolutions;

- Facilitating data collection, analysis, and storage, providing prosecutors with access to information and enabling effective utilization;

- Providing the capability to monitor activities in real-time, strengthening compliance with oversight and regulatory documents;

- Assisting in establishing good relations between prosecutor's offices and stakeholders, fostering collaboration and compassion in the process of resolving disputes;

- Facilitating thorough analysis and modelling to help prosecutors assess risks more comprehensively, enabling them to effectively mitigate potential threats and safeguard the security of general, specialized, and professional educational institutions;

- Optimizing expenses from allocated budgets by reducing costs in the distribution of digital management processes and resources, thus streamlining their usage from regulated budgets;

- Ensuring the qualitative refinement of responses to reports previously requested from mechanisms for order and reporting, thereby providing effective communication between prosecutor's offices and the community, shaping ideas and considerations for the betterment of social needs and concerns.

As our ideas continue to evolve, we reiterate D. Remezov's notion that "leveraging the possibilities of information technologies aids in gathering and reprocessing any

information, predicting and organizing supervisory activities, as well as in accounting and monitoring, creating convenient facilities for reporting".[10]

However, O. Shaporeva has pointed out the incapability of a certain percentage of the staff in prosecutor's offices to adapt to technologies. According to her, "Using information technologies does not guarantee that the prosecutors will acquire the necessary skills and competencies in performing their professional activities[11]." However, these ideas do not fully capture the situation. For instance, in our country, the "SEDO" electronic document exchange system has been implemented in the operations of prosecutor's offices, and with the implementation of the "Electronic Information Exchange" system, monitoring the circulation of documents and their execution is carried out[12].

Through this system, prosecutors are not only facing difficulties in handling work but are also gaining several conveniences. Specifically, the digitization of document circulation has accelerated the process of reviewing applications from individuals and legal entities, facilitating the acceleration of paper and postal service expenses (a total of 3.2 billion som was saved in 2021 through the "Electronic Document Circulation" system) [13].

In its own right, the electronic document circulation is a supportive system for organizing, reprocessing, structuring, and delivering information systematized to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the main operational process [14].

Indeed, as emphasized above, in the context of social relations and the progressive development of legal documents, the supervision of the prosecutor, which is one of the main duties of the prosecutor's office, is also required to be perfected simultaneously.

Observations indicate that in foreign countries, not only in general and special educational institutions, but also in the field of prosecutor supervision in all directions of prosecutorial activity, the possibility of utilizing the positive aspects of modern information technologies has been created. For example, in the Russian Federation, the Concept of "Digitization of the Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation by 2025"

was adopted with the Decree of the Chief Prosecutor No. 627 on September 17, 2017 [15].

Based on the aforementioned Concept, the following important tasks have been identified:

- Participating in the digitization of prosecutor's offices through legal, scientific, and practical means in collaboration with information technologies.

- Enhancing the effectiveness of supervision by establishing advanced and sophisticated information technologies for the reprocessing of unified information in all types of supervisory activities of prosecutor's offices.

- Increasing the influence of prosecutors in combating legal violations, eliminating causes and conditions that contribute to them, and countering them effectively.

- Ensuring timely, reliable, complete, and trustworthy information gathering on the state of affairs in activities related to the prevention of legal violations and crime, including remote, secluded areas [16].

Additionally, as emphasized by O.A. Insarov and B.V. Andreev, the information systems and complexes such as "NADZOR" AIK, "Archival Affairs OP" AIS, "CADRE" AIK, and "Parus" AIS have been developed in the Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation [17].

In particular, the "NADZOR" AIK is a system created primarily for the prosecutor's offices, providing services for electronic document circulation and management between government agencies and the prosecutor's office. This significantly reduces the workload and proves to be beneficial in terms of cost-effectiveness, resulting in a decrease in several budgetary allocations when accelerated (for reference - we have created the e-xat system).

Moreover, in Denmark, the system for electronic document exchange between institutions has been widely implemented. Various countries have adopted a single program that connects electronic information exchange systems together. This program

is called "XML-INFOSTURCTUREBASE." Furthermore, in this country, an e-book system has been introduced with the aim of converting paper submissions into electronic documents and then sending them through a secure mailbox. Each mailbox is filled with the citizen's personalized number. According to the analysis of foreign experience, one of the main priorities in the implementation process is to strengthen the electronic form of execution documents and provide them with legal force. Accordingly, in Sweden, about 75 percent of the processing activities are completed within a three-month period using the electronic system [18].

In Finland, a special law on the use of electronic equipment in government institutions was implemented from January 1, 2000. According to the law, an electronic document is an electronic message [19].

Today, in our country, the use of information technology in the activities of the prosecutor's offices, especially in the supervision of general, special, and professional educational institutions, is necessary to digitize the supervisory function.

Moreover, the powers of the prosecutor in carrying out supervisory tasks in general, special, and professional educational institutions are extensive, depending on the scope or direction of these supervisory areas.

During this time, the execution of the prosecutor's powers requires proactive action from the prosecutor, as individuals cannot independently protect and enforce their violated rights and legal interests at all times, necessitating additional guarantees for their rights to be secured [20].

From this perspective, ensuring the effectiveness of supervisory measures through advanced technologies in the supervision of general, special, and professional educational institutions is considered one of the most important tasks for ensuring legal compliance and improving the quality of education [21].

In the 139th decree of the Chief Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, titled "On Improving the Effectiveness of Supervision in Ensuring the Health of Unaccompanied Minors, in the Field of Social Protection, in the Field of Physical, Mental, and Moral Development, in Protecting Children Left without Parental Care, in

the Prevention of Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency, in Ensuring Legality during Inspections, Investigations, and Operational Activities up to the Completion of the Investigation," the tasks for enhancing supervision in the field of ensuring legality during inspections, investigations, and operational activities until the completion of the investigation are specified. It is evident that this area is considered broad from a surveillance perspective.

In our view, to enhance the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision in this area, there is an urgent need to develop new mechanisms for organizing and conducting comprehensive analysis using the latest advanced technologies. In this regard, I.B. Juraev suggests the necessity of establishing the "Unified Monitoring" and "Prosecutorial Supervision" electronic information systems to improve prosecutorial supervision [22]. Furthermore, according to M. Boboeva's emphasis, "the wide implementation of electronic document exchange between ministries, state committees, authorities, self-governing bodies, enterprises, institutions, and organizations with individuals in the process of enforcing compliance with laws in all areas contributes to ensuring legality, quality, and efficiency" [23].

Taking into account the relevance of the aforementioned ideas, creating an electronic document exchange system linking government agencies and prosecutor's offices in order to improve the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision and systematize the analysis of legal violations in the field appears to be essential in general, special, and professional educational institutions. Additionally, establishing a unified electronic platform to facilitate the implementation of prosecutorial supervision in general, special, and professional educational institutions using digital technologies seems imperative.

When referring to the digitization of prosecutorial supervision in general, special, and professional educational institutions, it implies "the possibility for a prosecuting officer performing in the field to conduct prosecutorial supervision online through an electronically digitized system" - as defined by the author, not necessarily aimed at final implementation.

In other words, the task of electronically registering information on each indicator relevant to the activities of government agencies overseeing supervisory activities in general, special, and professional educational institutions is assigned. This task involves not only prosecutors but also enabling other relevant active bodies and organizations in the field to access information on how laws are being observed, the occurrence of legal violations, and the specific measures taken to counteract them through the established electronic system. The development of such innovative systems not only enhances the effectiveness of prosecutorial supervision in terms of quality but also contributes to the comprehensive analysis of the legal activities of the relevant organizations actively involved in the field.

As mentioned earlier, no matter how well-organized administrative oversight is in educational institutions, the need for external oversight by prosecutor's offices may not be overlooked. The society's adherence to the fundamental principles of the state is one such imperative, whereby all institutions should operate within the framework of the law without impunity.

Emphasizing this point, the prosecutor's efforts in implementing oversight in general, special, and professional educational institutions involve gathering statistical information from supervisory institutions and organizations, as well as consulting relevant experts. This natural collaboration not only helps prosecutors but also allows institutions to conduct their activities more efficiently and identify shortcomings in time and in other aspects. Consequently, the establishment of an electronic document exchange system linking institutions and organizations in general, special, and professional educational institutions aims to facilitate the implementation of prosecutorial oversight.

Abroad, we observe the effective utilization of technological tools. For instance, in the United States, general educational institutions can access information through information systems established by the State Education Department, gathering data on student information, including academic evaluations, standardized test scores, and disciplinary measures. These systems facilitate the collection of data and the provision

of oversight reports or the creation of separate opportunities for monitoring and evaluation.

In the United Kingdom, schools often utilize the National Pupil Database (NPD) to share student information with the Department for Education (DfE). The NPD collects data on students' demographics, performance, achievements, and progress, aiding the government in monitoring and evaluating education policies.

In Brazil, prosecutors have access to information related to school education in collaboration with state courts and judicial authorities.

In light of the ideas presented above, it is suggested to supplement Article 21 of the "Law on the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan" with a second section stating, "In special cases of remote monitoring by the prosecutor's office in the field of law enforcement, it is possible to carry out such activities through an electronic platform, provided that the state, military, or personal information security is ensured during the inspection."

It is important to specify that implementing the highlighted reforms above may present certain challenges. In this regard, it is recommended to make effective use of the following analog monitoring measures.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Management of Tax Risks, Identification of Taxpayers (Tax Agents) at Risk and Organization of Tax Audits" dated January 7, 2021, by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the resolutions of the State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 29, 2018, "On Approval of the Procedure for Establishing a System for Analyzing Tax Risk in the State Tax Service Bodies," outline the measures for managing tax risks, identifying taxpayers (tax agents) at risk, and establishing a system for conducting tax audits. According to these documents, the tax authorities are to establish procedures for managing tax risks, identifying taxpayers (tax agents) at risk, and categorizing them according to the level of tax risk.

The main aspect of these reforms is the introduction of the "Risk Analysis" software in the state tax service bodies, enabling business entities to conduct tax risk

analysis automatically without human intervention. All of these measures are vital for the timely identification and prevention of potential violations that may occur in the field.

Furthermore, according to Presidential Decree No. PQ-240 dated May 11, 2022, starting from September 1, 2022, the government and management bodies, including their territorial divisions, state unitary enterprises and institutions, as well as organizations with more than 50% of state ownership, are required to conduct mandatory assessments of corruption risks and threats in their activities. In this regard, the "E-Anticor.uz" electronic platform has been introduced to present each function entrusted to state organizations to the Anti-Corruption Agency, with the aim of identifying and preventing existing risks and threats in the field.

In this regard, the establishment of a "risk analysis" system by the prosecutor's office is beneficial in implementing the oversight function, specifically in the field of general, specialized, and professional education, allowing for the timely identification and prevention of legal violations through the analysis of potential risks and threats. The introduction of this system enables the prosecutor's office to provide positive results without the need for physical inspection of the monitored object, saving time and costs. It also ensures that necessary information regarding the issues and deficiencies occurring in the activities is entered into the system, which might not have been recorded on time or may have been missed due to physical inspections. Additionally, the issuance of a prosecutor's notice (Warning, referred to as a new prosecutor oversight document in the "On the Prosecutor's Office" Law) for the entry of missing information or recommendations for eliminating identified shortcomings contributes to the reduction of legal violations in the field and broadens the scope of using preventive measures.

For instance, according to the Resolution No. 4342 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 29, 2019, concerning the comprehensive improvement of the activities of specialized educational institutions, the Ministry and agencies responsible for general or specialized education institutions, based on the

recommendations of the district (city) commission on children's issues, were instructed to allocate additional quotas beyond the admission quota of educational institutions, up to 5 per cent, for those who did not receive the recommendation for enrollment based on the conducted remote inspections. In cases where the results of remote inspections reveal situations exceeding this percentage or intentionally showing a decrease, the prosecutor's office plays a fundamental role in implementing the corresponding measures.

It is essential to note that the information mentioned above underscores the significance of conducting comprehensive oversight activities regularly through prosecutor oversight in identifying instances of legal violations and holding accountable those responsible for their occurrence. However, the proactive identification of inspection targets in the field of organizing inspections in general, specialized, and professional education institutions is initially challenging. Depending on the state of compliance with the law in the field, it is possible to evaluate the inspection object only after conducting the inspection.

In our opinion, the establishment of the "risk assessment and analysis" system in organizing the oversight of the prosecutor's office enhances effectiveness and optimizes inspection activities.

According to some researchers (Frank H. Knight, Daniel Kahneman, Amos Tversky, Paul Slovic, Douglas Hubbard), the introduction of such new systems in the field provides the following advantages:

1. Purposeful decision-making: Risk assessment systems provide a systematic and objective approach to assessing potential risks. They reduce the influence of subjective opinions and biases in the decision-making process by relying on information and empirical evidence.

2. Identification of hazards: These systems help identify potential risks or threats to human safety, the environment, or project processes.

3. Allocation of resources: Risk assessment enables effective resource allocation. Identifying the most critical risks allows organizations to direct their resources and strengths to areas with the highest potential impact.

4. Preventive measures: Risk assessment promotes proactive thinking and planning. It enables authorities and decision-makers to anticipate potential issues and take preventive measures before risks turn into significant problems.

5. Compliance with regulatory documents: The establishment of the risk assessment system ensures compliance with relevant laws and standards.

6. Enhanced communication: These systems facilitate communication among experts, policymakers, and the public.

7. Informed decision-making: Policymakers and stakeholders can make better-informed decisions based on the results of risk assessments.

8. Continuous improvement: Risk assessment systems promote constant evolution, considering the dynamic nature of new data and changes in social attitudes. Regular monitoring and updating facilitate the improvement of strategies for managing risks as conditions change over time.

9. Leveraging innovations: Risk assessment systems based on the identification and understanding of potential hazards can support the development and implementation of innovative technologies, products, or processes for safe operations.

Moreover, innovative technologies aimed at improving the quality of prosecutorial activities are available. We can highlight some examples based on the experience of foreign countries:

Information management systems (USA, Canada, UK, Germany, and Australia): Educational institutions use information management systems to handle various administrative tasks such as student assignments, progress tracking, grades, and disciplinary actions. Prosecutors can utilize these systems to access relevant data and adhere to educational regulations to identify trends and address potential issues within institutions.

Examples of such technology platforms include "Educational Institution Management Systems" and "Student Information Systems."

Surveillance and security systems (China, USA, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom): The installation of surveillance cameras and security systems in educational institutions helps prosecutors ensure the safety of students and staff. These technologies can also be useful in investigating and resolving incidents that may occur within the school environment.

Examples of such technology platforms include "CCTV Surveillance Systems" and "School Security Systems."

Biometric attendance systems (India, China, Japan, South Korea, and other countries): Biometric attendance systems, such as fingerprint or facial recognition scanners, can monitor the attendance of students and staff. This technology can be beneficial for prosecutors in ensuring compliance with institutional attendance regulations and identifying potential truancy cases.

Examples of such technology platforms include "Biometric Attendance Tracking Systems" and "Biometric Time and Attendance Systems."

Learning management systems (Used worldwide, including the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, Australia, and many other countries) (LMS): LMS platforms facilitate online education, course management, and communication between educators, students, and parents. Prosecutors can monitor these systems to ensure the provision of necessary courses and learning materials in accordance with the legal requirements of educational institutions.

An example of such a technology platform is "Learn Soft."

Security technologies for whistleblowers (Utilized in various countries, including the USA, Canada, Australia, the United Kingdom, and others): Anonymous reporting systems in educational institutions or the establishment of secure reporting hotlines enable students, staff, or parents to report any misconduct or unethical behavior occurring within the school premises. Subsequently, prosecutors can investigate reported issues and take appropriate measures accordingly.

Examples of such technology platforms include "Whistleblower Hotlines" and "Anonymous Reporting Systems."

Electronic learning and distance monitoring tools (Globally, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, the United States, China, India, Brazil, and others have shown significant utilization of these technologies): The advancement of distance learning has highlighted the significance of electronic learning platforms and distance monitoring tools. These technologies can assist prosecutors in ensuring the effective implementation of distance education and fulfilling their obligations to provide quality education to institutions' students.

Examples of such technology platforms include "E-Learning Platforms" and "Remote Learning Systems."

Data analysis and artificial intelligence (Countries such as the United States, China, Germany, and Japan have made significant progress in utilizing artificial intelligence): The collection and analysis of extensive data from educational institutions can be processed and analyzed using data analytics and AI technologies.

Examples of such technology platforms include "Data Analytics Tools" and "Artificial Intelligence Solutions for Education."

Building on the experiences mentioned above, the proposed completion of the second part of Article 31 of the Law "On the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan" suggests the following:

"...with regard to the documents that form the basis for the execution of punitive measures, which involve detaining, holding in custody, transferring to a pre-trial detention facility, depriving of liberty, and institutions executing medical coercion measures, as well as general education, specialized secondary, and professional education institutions that do not provide opportunities for comprehensive familiarization with all the premises, as well as imposing other measures of physical coercion or criminal-legal influence on individuals..."

In summary, the implementation of innovative methods in the supervision of compliance with the law in general, specialized secondary, and professional educational institutions by the prosecutor's office yields several positive results:

Firstly, Efficiency: Information technologies streamline the process of collecting and analyzing information, enabling prosecutors to utilize relevant data more easily and provide prompt responses to emerging issues.

Secondly, Security: These technologies ensure security in educational institutions, facilitating the identification and elimination of any violations.

Thirdly, Evidence-based Investigations: The use of information and technologies aids in the creation of robust evidence and arguments for effective legal actions, if necessary.

Fourthly, Preventive Measures: Prosecutors can take proactive measures to address emerging issues in educational institutions through active supervision and enforcement of necessary regulations.

Fifthly, Timely Interventions: Swift interventions facilitated by real-time monitoring and reporting can help protect the rights and well-being of students and staff.

Sixthly, Compliance and Standardization: The adoption of information technologies ensures that the prosecutor's oversight is precise and comprehensive, assisting in the enforcement of rigorous standardization across various educational institutions.

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